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Divinity of Dharma vis-à-vis Negotiations and Reconciliation in Warfare: A Study in Relation to The Mahabharata, Ramayana and Trojan War

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Abstract:

Negotiation and reconciliation are the key aspects of everyone's life; negotiation has been an inherent tradition that has been continuous since ancient times. Preceding the war, key negotiations took place before the Mahabharata, the Ramayana, and even before the Trojan war. This paper will evaluate the three negotiations that took place before the war, led by key figures such as Krishna, Angada, Menelaus, and Odysseus, respectively. Numerous negotiations and reconciliation sessions took place in these wars, but we shall specifically focus on the negotiations that occurred just before the war. This paper will critically study all these negotiations with precision and exactitude.

Keywords: Negotiations, Reconciliation, Mahabharata, Ramayana, Trojan War.

I

Negotiation is an essential part of everyone's life; negotiation is a process of communicating and bargaining to achieve a mutually beneficial outcome. In daily life, we negotiate for everything we buy, from vegetables to groceries; sometimes we engage in negotiations and bargaining with a focus and some strategy. Bargaining and negotiating are among the few skills that are necessary to survive in today's world. Negotiations can take many forms, and we must employ different skills for various aspects of the negotiation process. In

our history, which has shaped our culture, whether through the Ramayana or the Mahabharata, there are numerous instances where negotiations and reconciliation played a significant role.

However, there is a manner of negotiations derived from a particular tradition just before the war; the negotiations that were carried out before the war are part of reconciliation efforts informed by a distinguished Sanatana tradition, dating back to ancient times and spanning years. Negotiations often take place just before war breaks out, as seen in the wars of Ramayana, Mahabharata, and even the Trojan war. Also, in World War I, negotiations conducted through Bismarck's Diplomacy, the Reinsurance Treaty, the Treaty of London (1915), the Sykes-Picot Agreement (1916), and the Treaty of Brest-Litovsk (1918). In World War II, the Munich Agreement (1938) and the German-Soviet Non-Aggression Pact (1939) were key negotiations that preceded the war. Essentially, negotiation before a war is an integral part of any significant or minor conflict.

Why is negotiation an essential process just before the war? Peace has no other option; peace is more important than anything else. Peace comes at a cost; that is why people put their egos aside for negotiations and try to find common ground. Peace is the real reason behind all the negotiations just before the war, as both sides know that whatever the outcome, there will be destruction on both sides, there will be loss of lives, property, etc. In the Mahabharata, Krishna, until the last moment before the war began, said that war is the last option, and he tried everything from his side to avoid it; he insisted on peace and wanted just five villages (Vyasa, Udyog Parva), which sometimes people can assume was a weak step.² Still, Krishna wanted to prevent the war through his negotiation skills. In this paper, we explore the concepts of negotiation and reconciliation in the context of the Mahabharata, as well as the Ramayana. Also, in this paper, we will delve into the themes of negotiation and reconciliation as illustrated in the Mahabharata and the Ramayana, while also drawing connections to the dynamics observed during the Trojan war.

II

In the Mahabharata, numerous instances of emissaries and negotiations are recorded. The main negotiation, which is still discussed, was the Krishna negotiations when he went to Hastinapur; even after a failed attempt, he asked for five villages to avoid war, which has been recognised as a classic in the history of negotiations. All these negotiations and bargaining talks took place in the fifth Parva of the Mahabharata, known as the Udyoga Parva; it covers the return of the Pandavas from exile, as well as the diplomacy and preparation for war from both sides.

The Mahabharata was a fight between the Pandavas and the Kauravas; it was a long and complex story of a feud with numerous branches. Still, importantly, the Pandavas, led by their eldest brother Yudhisthira, wanted to reclaim Indraprastha, the city they had built. Pandavas had been exiled for 14 years after having been defeated in a dice game; having returned, they wanted Indraprastha back, and the Prince of Hastinapur, Duryodhana, the eldest son of King Dhritarashtra, did not wish to part with Indraprastha. Then, consequently, negotiations began on both sides. (Vyasa, *Mahabharata*)

Before Krishna, as mentioned in the text, it was the Rajpurohit of King Drupad who first went for the negotiation; he was an erudite man with the commands of the Vedas, which have remained a mark of perfection through the ages. He explained the matter promptly and requested the Indraprastha without any hesitation. The Pandavas' side initiated the first round of negotiations, which began with the minor section known as the Sanjayyan Sub-Parva. The first messenger sent by the Pandavas was the Rajpurohit of King Drupada as the negotiator, or, more accurately, as a messenger; the command he received from the Pandavas was to employ elegant words and seek blessings from the elders of the Kauravas' side; apart from this, he conveyed a message requesting the return of Indraprastha; after listening to Rajpurohit

Duryodhana, Shakuni, and Karna became angry, but the senior people of the Kaurava assembly listened to him; Duryodhana and Karna became angry with Rajpurohit as he demanded Indraprastha, and he spoke ferociously about it; then, the senior members of that Sabha, Pitamaha Bhishma, Dronacharya, and Kripacharya, cooled down the temperature. Rajpurohit asked for the answer from King Dhritarashtra, but the King then asked him to return, saying he would send his message through a mediator, as he had promised. (Udyog Parva, Vyasa, Chapter 20-21)

The next rounds of talks, in which Sanjay, Charioteer of Dhritarashtra, was involved, are also included in this Sub-Parva. After the Pandavas' attempt, Dhritarashtra sent Sanjay, a virtuous man with a calm and composed mind, to convey that the Pandavas should stay and not insist on Indraprastha. Sanjay went there; he was a calm, composed man, and the Pandavas were gracious people in every way. They gave him lots of respect and then asked for the message that the King had sent. Sanjay delivered the message that King Dhritarashtra wanted them to stay wherever they were and live peacefully, which made the Pandavas angry. Finally, they sent a message of war through Sanjay, and it decided that war would happen when Sanjay returned to Hastinapur. However, Shri Krishna wanted another chance for peace, as there was no other option available. Peace is the ultimate right thing to have, but not at the cost of cowardice. (Udyog Parva, Vyasa, Chapter 22-32)

Krishna himself decided to go for the negotiation, as it had not succeeded in the previous attempts; Krishna wanted to ensure that every possible deed should be done for the peace. Nowadays, people believe that Krishna could have stopped the war, unaware that Krishna had tried everything to achieve peace. Even when Krishna went as an emissary, most of the members of the Pandavas' side were unhappy, including Draupadi and Bhima.

It was an intensive discussion in the Udyog Parva about the entire event, specifically Krishna's visit to Hastinapur and how he carried it out. Dhritarashtra wanted to make Krishna happy, so he arranged everything accordingly; they even arranged Dushasana's palace for Krishna's stay, as Dushasana's palace is new and better built than Duryodhana's; There was also an arrangement for a sumptuous meal for Krishna; it is rare for any negotiator to have that kind of hospitality from the enemy at war; however, Krishna did not yield to the request, as he found it morally and consciously wrong; he put forth a theory that one can be entitled to hospitality as a guest or someone in need of food, and he declined the hospitality on those grounds; Krishna went to Vidura's house for a meal; at this point, Duryodhana became angry, but he was unable to do anything. (Udyog Parva, Vyasa, Chapter 72-89)

The next day, the council of Kaurava arranged for all the ministers and dignitaries present to have a special chair for Krishna, which was met with great respect from King Dhritarashtra and all the dignitaries. In the first address, he conveyed greetings from the Pandavas' side to all the kings, Dhritarashtra, Bhishma, and Dronacharya. Then he proceeded to recount everything from the beginning, explaining how Shakuni had cheated them, how Draupadi had been insulted, and how the Pandavas deserved Indraprastha back. Krishna explained in great detail how the Pandavas endured their pain and other atrocities; despite this, they did not retaliate. He explained the great injustice that Shakuni did to them, what injustice was done to Draupadi in the front of whole gathering, despite these they endured everything, whatever was done to Bhima in childhood, whatever was attempting to be done to them in Lakshagraha, even after that they remained silent and accepted all the ill treatment and bad fate to them. Krishna added that the Pandavas duly completed 13 years of exile and one year of incognito exile, so it is their right that Indraprastha, which they had built with great hard work, should be restored to them. Duryodhana heard everything and rejected Krishna's proposal, which angered the elders of the Kauravas assembly. Bhishma intervened, as did King Dhritarashtra, but

Duryodhana remained unmoved. Then, Krishna put another proposal to avoid the war; he asked for the five villages named Kusasthala, Vrikasthala, Makandi, Varnavratha, and one more, according to the wishes of Duryodhana or Dhritarashtra.² Then, finally, Duryodhana said, 'I will not give them even an inch of land.' Krishna then replied with eloquence, which made Duryodhana angry, and he ordered the arrest of Krishna. Krishna was the incarnation of Shri Hari, and we all know what happened after that.¹ This was a period of intense deliberation, in which everyone involved, even Dhritarashtra, called Gandhari to exhort Duryodhana. However, Duryodhana remained steadfast in his stance and never wavered in his thoughts. (Udyog Parva, Vyasa, Chapter 124-131)

This negotiation has its roots in the history of war, as Krishna himself decided to go as the messenger of peace with a strategic negotiator. Krishna admits in the Mahabharata that war is the last resort, so we must utilise all the options for peace, and he puts his best effort into bringing peace through his negotiation skills. Krishna's calm and composed demeanour in the Kaurava Sabha was opposite to Duryodhana's relentless attempts to provoke him. Despite the elders' efforts to reason with Duryodhana, his stubbornness was a constant obstacle, frustrating every negotiation and peace attempt. (Udyog Parva, Vyasa, Chapter 124-131)

This negotiation by Krishna shall be an example for posterity; this negotiation helps people understand that peace is everything, even at the cost of some compromises, as Krishna was willing to give up Indraprastha and only asked for five villages.² This chapter of the Mahabharata offers guidance in various aspects of life, including management, diplomacy, and business.

III

In the Trojan war, there were attempts made to achieve peace, as mentioned in the *Cypria*, a lost epic of Greek literature; *The Trojan Women*, written by Euripides; and the

Chronicle of the Trojan War in Latin, written by Dictys Cretensis. *Cypria* is a prequel to the *Iliad*, which mentions things that lead to the Trojan War. The process of war initiated when Paris, the Prince of Troy, took Helen, the wife of Menelaus, the King of Sparta, with him. Menelaus himself went to the negotiations, which are particularly interesting from the Eastern perspective on negotiations, where the King never engages in negotiations, as they always sent ambassadors or intellectuals. This negotiation is not found in Homer's *Iliad*, as it directly starts in the 9th year of the Trojan War; Homer does not put the incidents that led to the war in any of his writings.

Menelaus and Odysseus, who was the King of Ithaca, went for the negotiations. Odysseus was a cunning but brilliant man on the Greeks' side, as he was one of the few people who survived the war. Here are the accounts that say about the attempt at negotiations for peace before the war:

Euripides (480–406 BCE), a Greek tragedian, wrote in his play *The Trojan Women* that, through the character of Hecuba (Queen of Troy), he refers to the envoys and the rejection of the Greeks' request. She recalls how the Greeks initially came for peace.

"When the Greeks came to Troy at first, they did not come with arms, but sent envoys...
desiring to take back Helen in peace..."

(*Trojan Women*, Euripides 858–862)

Euripides, in his other works, particularly in *Helen*, also mentions and refers to this incident in lines 89-120.

There is one more authentic source in Latin, written by Dictys Cretensis, named the *Chronicle of the Trojan War*. In his book, 1 Chapter 6, he mentions this diplomatic mission in great detail.

It says:

"Menelaus and Odysseus were sent as ambassadors to demand Helen. Priam received them honourably, but Paris refused to give up Helen. Priam was indecisive, swayed by his sons."

This account supports the story of a peaceful embassy rejected by Paris and ultimately by the Trojans. As more and more sources say that Priam, the King of Troy, was ready to negotiate, but due to the stubbornness of Paris, he could not do much about it; It feels like the story of the Mahabharata, where King Dhritarashtra was ready to negotiate and, in some ways, did not want war; however, due to the rigidity of his son, he went to war and rejected the negotiations that the Pandavas and Krishna were offering; both the Mahabharata war and the Trojan War negotiations share a similar approach in handling negotiations.

Evidence from the classical text is sufficient to describe the negotiations that took place in the City of Troy just before the Trojan War. Still, there is little detail about the talks between Menelaus and Odysseus and the Trojans at the negotiation table. It is challenging to find concise information about the negotiations that occur in the city of Troy. There is a significant difference between the Ramayana, the Mahabharata, and the Trojan war. In the Ramayana and Mahabharata, there is a wealth of detail about the negotiations that took place just before the war. However, there is little substantive evidence about the negotiations in the Trojan war, which may indicate the Historicity of the Ramayana and Mahabharata.

IV

In the Ramayana, King Ravana abducted Sita, the wife of Shri Ram, a member of the Kshatriya clan, whose heritage included an intense fervour for war and battle. Shri Ram, Laxman, and Sita were in exile for fourteen years, during which they lived in the forest. Ravana abducted Sita by assuming the guise of a saint; then, after some time, Shri Ram found out that Ravana had abducted Sita and taken her to Lanka, which was on the other side of the sea. They met with Hanuman ji, Sugriva, and others, and prepared an army of monkeys, all of which were

well-trained. Just before the war, Shri Ram sent Angad to negotiate at the last moment in Lanka, but Ravana was adamant, so the attempt failed. Angada put their offer of negotiation to the Ravana assembly, but heated talks exchanged between Ravana and Angada. This negotiation is given in Chapter 41 of Yuddha Kanda in the Valmiki Ramayana.

Angada was an honest man with a profound understanding of values and morality, as well as a clear grasp of dharma. Just before the war, Angada was sent as an emissary to avoid the war. Ravana does not even give him a place to sit, so Angada prepares a seat for himself with his tail, as he was a Vanara. Angad's father, Bali, had already had a significant fight with Ravana, so Ravana reminded him of his father, Bali, as Shri Ram killed him; Ravana tried to persuade him, but Angada, with eloquence, reminded Ravana about the defeat he had suffered at the hands of his father, Bali. (Yuddha Kand, Valmiki, Chapter 41)

Angada comes with crisp clarity of thought and puts everything straight in the Sabha of Ravana; first, Ravana mocks this process of negotiation, thinking Rama is afraid of him; Angada promptly answers him with straight talk. Ravana insulted Shri Ram with some mocking words. Angad pointed this out and answered back.³ There was a heated exchange of words between Ravana and Angada, as Ravana did not want to show any courtesy to the emissary. Ravana made the conclusive statement: 'Go and tell your Shri Ram that I will not return you Janaki, if you have the guts, fight and take it with you.' Angada responded with some harsh words, and then Ravana became angry. He ordered the arrest of Angada. Angada then challenged the whole Sabha to remove his leg from there. Everyone tried, even the son of Ravana, Meghnad, and Ravana himself, but failed; Angada returned from there, humiliating all the people present there, including the King and the Prince. This incident gave rise to a famous phrase in Hindi, as people began to say "Angad's Foot," which signifies unyielding strength.⁴ (*Ramcharitmanas*, Tulsidas, Lanka Kand)

In the negotiations of Shri Krishna and Angada, there is one significant similarity: both Duryodhana and Ravana wanted to take them to prison, as they became angry with the negotiator and their clear, crisp talks. However, Krishna and Angada possessed a special power that counteracted it, enabling them to return safely from there. The negotiation in the Ramayana is unique, as the opposing side refuses to engage in any talks.

V

Negotiation is a fundamental aspect, dating back to ancient times, as evidenced by the negotiations that preceded the great wars; negotiation did not yield success in three of the biggest wars, but it was a part of the warfare in every case, as the process is more important than the result. Negotiation is a valuable skill that requires bravery, eloquence, and honesty. We have seen that in all three, the war negotiators were skilful and wise. Krishna himself was the incarnation of God, bestowed with all the excellent skills. Menelaus himself was the King of Sparta, and Odysseus was a devious man with a clever mind. They were the ideal beings available for negotiating on behalf of the Greeks. Angada was also a courageous man who was well-versed in the principles of dharma. One of the critical aspects of negotiation before war is that it always requires the presence of erudite men.

In the Mahabharata and Ramayana, numerous similarities exist, which may be a tradition rooted in the Sanatana culture that embodies truth and honesty. Krishna and Angad, as well as Rajpurohit, were all very vocal and straightforward about righteousness and their views; due to their relatively straightforward talk, Duryodhana and Ravana were severely pricked. The intolerance of Duryodhana and Ravana was so extreme that they sought to arrest the mediator, an incredibly drastic step in those times.

In the negotiation of the Mahabharata, when Krishna presented his matter to the Kaurava Sabha, there were some people, such as Bhishma, Dronacharya, and Kripacharya, who

netrābhyāṁ nastataścaiva śrotrābhyāṁ ca samantataḥ |

prādurāsanmahāraudrāḥ sadhūmāḥ pāvakārciṣaḥ |

romakūpeṣu ca tathā sūryasyeva marīcayaḥ ||

3/ dehi me pañca grāmāṇi pāṇḍavāyaiva kevalam |

tānityeva vadāmate tatra pāpaṁ na vidyate ||

na ca rāmaṁ parājetuṁ śakto rāvaṇa kiñcana |

sarve te vinaśiṣyanti yudhyanto rāmatejasā ||

4/ pag dhareu kapi bhūpāl jū, chalai na kou chaleu |

simhāsan te sasi sir gayo, rāvanu lāji pareu ||

5/ simhāsan te sasi sir gayo, rāvanu lāji pareu ||

simhāsan te sasi sir gayo, rāvanu lāji pareu ||

simhāsan te sasi sir gayo, rāvanu lāji pareu ||

simhāsan te sasi sir gayo, rāvanu lāji pareu ||

Works Cited:

Vyasa, Ved. *Mahabharata (Udyog Parva)*. Gita Press Gorakhpur, 2020.

Debroy, Bibek. *Mahabharata (Udyog Parva)*. Penguin Publication, 2015.

Valmiki. *Ramayana (Yuddha Kand)*. Gita Press Gorakhpur, 2021.

Tulsidas. *Ramcharitmanas (Lanka Kand)*. Gita Press Gorakhpur, 2014.

Euripides. *The Trojan Women*. Cambridge University Press, 2012.

Davies, Malcolm. *The Cypria*. Harvard University Press, 2019.

Cretensis, Dictys. *Chronicle of the Trojan War*. Trans. R.M. Frazer. Indiana University Press,
1966.